

INTERLAMINAR STRESS RECOVERY OF MULTILAYER COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY

Despite their merits, composites have weakness in transverse strength making them prone to failures such as delamination when subjected to high interlaminar stresses. Onset of delamination can only be accurately predicted if an appropriate evaluation of the interlaminar stress fields is obtained.

An efficient post-processing recovery procedure evaluating interlaminar stress fields of moderately thick-thin multilayer composite structures has been presented in the previous work of the authors. Comparisons with exact solutions of benchmark problems have confirmed the reliability of the approach.

In the present paper, this procedure is combined with the commercial finite element software ABAQUS 6.8. Attention is also addressed to multilayer shell structures.

Keywords: Layered shell structures, Intra-interlaminar stress fields.

INTRODUCTION

Increasing use of composite laminates in a wide range of applications has underlined the need to understand their major interlaminar mode of failure, delamination. Composites are prone to delamination when subjected to high interlaminar stresses. Once interlaminar stress fields are evaluated, location and crack form are usually assumed in advance in most of the theoretical studies on onset of delamination. Consequently, an appropriate evaluation of interlaminar stresses leads to an accurate prediction of the failure mechanism.

Most research activity has been focused on procedures aimed at improving the accuracy of finite element solutions obtained by means of displacements based models. C^0 continuous elements usually lack the characteristics of having continuous stresses at the inter-element boundary. Stress distributions from such elements are inclined to exhibit oscillatory behavior, especially for thin plates, making the judgement of results difficult [1].

An efficient interlaminar stress recovery technique has been presented in the previous work of the authors [2]. This procedure is based on a domain decomposition approach for

the parallel finite element solution of equilibrium equations, i.e. Finite Element Tearing and Interconnecting method [3]. The spatial domain is partitioned into a set of totally disconnected subdomains and Lagrange multipliers are introduced to enforce compatibility at the interfacial nodes. Taking into account multilayer composite structures, every layer is considered as a single subdomain. Consequently, connecting forces are obtained at the interfacial nodes of the different subdomains and smooth interlaminar transverse stress fields are produced based on equilibrium considerations.

The discrete model has been generated by means of a simple linear solid-shell element [4, 5]. Conforming meshes have been considered. A consistent variational recovery procedure has also been implemented in order to recover in-plane stress fields [6].

Plates of various geometries subjected to different mechanical loadings have been taken into account. Comparisons with exact solutions of benchmark problems have confirmed the reliability of the approach.

This procedure is herein combined with the commercial finite elements software ABAQUS 6.8. A detailed description is reported in the next section. Attention is also addressed to the analysis of multilayered shell structures.

INTERLAMINAR STRESS RECOVERY

The post-processing stress recovery procedure described in the previous section is herein combined with the commercial finite element software ABAQUS 6.8. The discrete model is obtained in ABAQUS/Standard by means of an 8-node linear brick incompatible modes element (*C3D8I*).

Attention is readdressed at the determination of the interfacial conditions between the different layers providing the connecting forces. The interlaminar boundary is modelled as a contact zone and interlaminar stresses are later recovered from the contact loads that satisfy force equilibrium at the interface. Abaqus/Standard offers several contact formulations [7]. Once master and slave surfaces are assigned, discretization of the contact pair is of primary importance. Surface-to-surface contact discretization is herein adopted which enforces the contact conditions over the slave surface in an average sense. This assumption provides a more accurate contact pressure accuracy. The mechanical contact properties are based on a contact pressure-overclosure relationship that prevents surfaces from separating once they have come into contact, i.e. tied contact. This constraint enforcement is obtained by penalty function method. This relationship is combined with a rough friction tangential model able to prevent relative sliding motion between two contacting surfaces. Lagrange multipliers are used to enforce this constraint.

Output variables required by the complete stress recovery procedure are retrieved from the output database file of ABAQUS by means of a Python script. Once the complete stress fields are obtained, the data is sent back and visualized in the updated output database.

The reliability of the aforementioned procedure is confirmed in the next section. Benchmark problems regarding plate and shell structures are analyzed and the obtained responses are compared with available exact solutions.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

Simply supported plate subjected to bisinusoidal pressure load

A simply supported cross-ply ($0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$) square plate under bisinusoidally distributed pressure load (of intensity p_z) is analyzed. The length and thickness of the plate is denoted by “ a ” and “ H ” respectively. Material properties of a ply in its principal material coordinates are given as

$$\frac{E_L}{E_T} = 25, \quad \frac{G_{LT}}{E_T} = 0.5, \quad \frac{G_{TT}}{E_T} = 0.2, \quad \nu_{LT} = \nu_{TT} = 0.25,$$

where the subscript L refers to the direction of the fibers in the ply and T denotes the transverse directions of the lamina. The individual plies are taken to be of equal thickness. Obtained results are compared with the exact elasticity solution of Pagano [8].

Conforming meshes between the layers are considered. Unless differently stated, the in-plane mesh consists of 14×14 elements, and the through-the-thickness mesh is the minimum required for applying the interlaminar stress recovery procedure at the points of interest. In the case under consideration values of intralaminar transverse stresses in the middle of every layer are reported and as a consequence, three more fictitious interfaces are required in these locations for a total number of six layers. Stresses are normalized according to the following formulae:

$$\begin{aligned} (\tau'_{xz}, \tau'_{yz}) &= \frac{1}{p_z S} (\tau_{xz}, \tau_{yz}), \quad \sigma'_{zz} = \frac{1}{p_z} \sigma_{zz}, \\ (\sigma'_{xx}, \sigma'_{yy}, \tau'_{xy}) &= \frac{1}{p_z S^2} (\sigma_{xx}, \sigma_{yy}, \tau_{xy}). \end{aligned}$$

where $S = a/H$.

As stated in the introduction, stress distribution from C^0 continuous elements exhibit oscillatory behavior, especially for thin plates, making the judgement of results difficult. Consequently, a laminate of aspect ratio $S = 100$ is first taken into account. Figure 1 shows convergence analyses of the recovered stress fields related to the interlaminar transverse shear stress τ'_{xz} at the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ interface and the in-plane stress τ'_{xy} at $z = H/2$. An excellent agreement with the exact solution and fast convergence is obtained. It is worth to underline that smooth distributions of the stress fields are directly produced without considering any additional smoothing technique or even more refined mesh. Similar consideration can be respectively done for the other transverse and in-plane stress distributions.

The same laminate has been analyzed in the work done by Dakshina-Moorthy and Reddy [9]. Regarding the structural symmetry only a quarter of the plate has been taken into account. An in-plane mesh of $[8 \times 8]$ nine-node quadratic elements and a mesh of linear Lagrange elements through the thickness of the laminate has been considered. The bottom two layers have been modelled as a single numerical layer, and the through-the-thickness mesh has been the minimum required for modelling the interface of interest as a contact zone. The interlaminar stresses have been calculated and compared using three different approaches: (1) equilibrium based stress recovery procedure (at nodes); (2) from constitutive relations (at integration points); and (3) variationally optimal stress

recovery procedure (at integration points). As shown in fig. 2, all the aforementioned procedures have generated severe oscillations as far as transverse stresses are concerned. Smoothing techniques are required. Moreover, it is shown that stress fields generated from constitutive relations and those from variational approaches may lead to not so accurate estimations.

In order to demonstrate the accuracy of the proposed procedure in analyzing moderately thick plates, a laminate of aspect ratio $S = 50$ is also taken into account. Comparisons between the thickness plots of the obtained transverse stress fields and the exact solution are shown in fig. 3 at points of major interest. Once again an excellent response is provided and fast convergence is reached.

Thickness plots obtained by ABAQUS considering three different elements are also reported. The considered elements are respectively the 8-node linear brick incompatible modes $C3D8I$, the 20-node quadratic brick $C3D20R$, and the linear 8-node $C3D8R$. Based on the element formulation, stresses are recovered at integration points by means of constructive models that are derived from either variational principles or other energy laws [7]. The linear $C3D8R$ element does not provide single valued results at the interfaces but, as expected, constant values along the thickness of every single layer due to the adopted reduced integration technique. A similar response of the transverse shear stresses is also obtained by means of the $C3D8I$ element despite the fact that the reduced integration technique is not involved in the formulation. Moreover, in the evaluation of the transverse normal stress are produced highly inaccurate results. The quadratic $C3D20R$ element does not produce an accurate estimation of the transverse shear stress τ'_{yz} . Moreover, not converging interlaminar stresses are generated between the 0° and 90° plies. However, a good overall response is obtained as far as the transverse shear τ'_{xz} and normal σ'_{zz} stresses are concerned.

A comparison between the obtained in-plane stress σ'_{xx} distributions is also shown in fig. 4. An appropriate response is basically obtained in all the cases with the expected exception of the linear $C3D8R$ element. Same kind of conclusion can be formulated for the other in-plane stress fields.

On the one hand, variational post-processing procedures can be, in general, clearly adopted in the evaluation of the in plane stress fields of multilayered composite plates, on the other hand the evaluation of the transverse stress fields requires more accurate approaches if neither refined expensive meshes nor elements based on higher order theories are taken into account. Additional results calculated in points of major interest are reported in tab. 1 where a laminate of aspect ratio $S = 20$ is also considered.

(a) Convergence of the interlaminar transverse shear stress τ'_{xz} with different in-plane meshes.

(b) Convergence of the in-plane stress τ'_{xy} with different in-plane meshes.

Figure 1: Convergence of the recovered stress fields, $S = 100$.

Figure 2: Shear stress distribution τ'_{xz} at the interlaminar surface $[0/90]$ and $y = a/2$ obtained by Reddy and Dakshina-Moorthy [9] considering different approaches, $S = 100$.

Figure 3: Thickness plot comparison between the transverse stresses obtained with different approaches and the exact solution, $S = 50$.

Figure 4: Thickness plot comparison between the in-plane stress σ'_{xx} obtained with different approaches and the exact solution, $S = 50$.

Table 1: Comparison with the exact solution of the recovered stress fields concerning different values of aspect ratio a/H .

S		$\sigma'_{xx}(\frac{a}{2}, \frac{b}{2}, \pm\frac{1}{2})$	$\sigma'_{yy}(\frac{a}{2}, \frac{b}{2}, \pm\frac{1}{6})$	$\tau'_{xz}(0, \frac{b}{2}, 0)$	$\tau'_{yz}(\frac{a}{2}, 0, 0)$	$\tau'_{xy}(0, 0, \pm\frac{1}{2})$	$\sigma'_{zz}(\frac{a}{2}, \frac{b}{2}, H/6)$
20	EXACT	± 0.552	± 0.210	0.3846	0.0938	∓ 0.0234	0.7398
	EQUIL/VAR	± 0.547	± 0.207	0.3845	0.0938	∓ 0.0229	0.7429
50	EXACT	± 0.541	± 0.185	0.3934	0.0842	∓ 0.0216	0.7406
	EQUIL/VAR	± 0.536	± 0.183	0.3928	0.0841	∓ 0.0212	0.7436
100	EXACT	± 0.539	± 0.181	0.3946	0.0828	∓ 0.0213	0.7407
	EQUIL/VAR	± 0.534	± 0.179	0.3926	0.0823	∓ 0.0209	0.7434

Varadan and Bhaskar's Cylindrical Shells

Varadan and Bhaskar [10] have considered three dimensional elasticity solutions for finite length cross-ply laminated cylindrical shells (see fig. 5(a)), simply supported at both ends and subjected to transverse sinusoidal pressure at the internal surface

$$P_{zb^1}^* = P_{zb^1} \sin \frac{m\pi z}{L} \cos n\theta, \quad (1)$$

where $m = 1$ and $n = 4$. $L/R_0 = 4$ where L and R_0 are respectively the length and the mean radius of the cylindrical shell.

Regarding the structural symmetry only quadrant of cylindrical shell and finite cylinder is modelled in the finite element analysis. The deformed and un-deformed configuration of the adopted model are reported in fig. 5(b).

The mechanical data are $E_L/E_T = 25$, $G_{LT}/E_T = 0.5$, $G_{TT}/E_T = 0.2$, $\nu_{LT} = \nu_{TT} = 0.25$. The following lamination schemes are herein considered: a two-layered ($90^\circ/0^\circ$) shell (90° for the outer layer and 0° for the inner layer), and a three-layered ($90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ$) shell. The individual plies are taken to be of equal thickness.

(a) Circular cylindrical shell.

(b) Adopted model: quadrant of cylindrical shell and finite cylinder.

Figure 5: Varadan and Bhaskar's cylindrical shell

Results are presented for values of aspect ratio $S = R_0/h = 50, 100$ in terms of the

following non-dimensional parameters

$$\sigma'_r = \sigma_r/P_{zb^1}; \quad (\sigma'_\theta, \sigma'_z, \tau'_{\theta z}) = (10/P_{zb^1}S^2)(\sigma_\theta, \sigma_z, \tau_{\theta z});$$

$$(\tau'_{rz}, \tau'_{r\theta}) = (10/P_{zb^1}S)(\tau_{rz}, \tau_{r\theta});$$

For convenience a non-dimensional transverse coordinate ξ varying from -0.5 at the inner surface to 0.5 at the outer surface is defined. The value $\xi = 0$ refers to the geometric middle surface.

The in-plane mesh consists of 30 elements along the cylindrical coordinate θ and of 20 elements along the cylindrical coordinate z . The through-the-thickness mesh is the minimum required for applying the procedure at the points of interest. As for the simply supported plate previously analyzed, one fictitious interface is introduced in the middle of every layer.

A three-layered ($90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ$) shell of aspect ratio $S = 100$ is first taken into account. Comparisons between the thickness plots at points of maximum value of the obtained transverse stress fields and the exact solution are shown in fig. 6. Thickness plots obtained by ABAQUS are also reported for comparison. Compared to the simply supported plate, the same kind of conclusions can be formulated. The quadratic *C3D20R* element produces a good overall response, but less accurate compared to the presented equilibrium based procedure since an overestimation of the transverse normal stress σ'_r is encountered. Moreover, inaccurate results may be obtained in the areas where the boundary conditions are applied. An example is shown in fig. 7 where is reported the tangential plot starting from $\theta = 0^\circ$ up to $\theta = 45^\circ$ of the transverse normal stress σ'_r at the $[90/0]$ interface and $z = L/2$.

The accuracy of the transverse stress fields provided by the quadratic *C3D20R* element gets worse when a two-layered ($90^\circ/0^\circ$) shell is considered (see fig.8). The transverse shear stress distribution $\tau'_{r\theta}$ is not as accurate as in the three-layered shell previously analyzed and highly inaccurate results are in particular obtained for the transverse normal stress σ'_r . The equilibrium based procedure produces once again excellent results in both cases compared to the exact solution.

As far as the in-plane stress fields are concerned, the conclusions formulated for the simply supported plate can be herein extended for the cross-ply laminated cylindrical shells. Additional results calculated at points of maximum value are reported in tab. 2.

Figure 6: Thickness plot comparison between the transverse stresses obtained with different approaches and the exact solution, three-layered ($90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ$) shell, $S = 100$.

Figure 7: Tangential plot of the transverse normal stress σ_r' at the $[90/0]$ interface and $z = L/2$, three-layered ($90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ$) shell, $S = 100$.

Figure 8: Thickness plot comparison between the transverse stresses obtained with different approaches and the exact solution, two-layered ($90^\circ/0^\circ$) shell, $S = 100$.

Table 2: Comparison with the exact solution of the recovered stress fields.

S		σ'_θ ($\xi = \mp \frac{1}{2}$)	σ'_z ($\xi = \mp \frac{1}{2}$)	$\tau'_{\theta z}$ ($\xi = \mp \frac{1}{2}$)	τ'_{rz} ($\xi = -\frac{1}{6}$)	$\tau'_{r\theta}$ ($\xi = 0$)	σ'_r ($\xi = 0$)
50 ($90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ$)	EXACT	-3.987	-0.0225	-0.0760	0.0894	-3.491	-4.85
		3.930	0.0712	-0.0118			
	EQUIL/VAR	-3.930	-0.0229	-0.0754	0.0897	-3.466	-4.88
		3.882	0.0704	-0.0117			
100	EXACT	-3.507	-0.0018	-0.1038	0.1223	-3.127	-8.30
		3.507	0.0838	-0.0478			
	EQUIL/VAR	-3.466	-0.0019	-0.1028	0.1220	-3.102	-8.35
		3.466	0.0832	-0.0472			
50 ($90^\circ/0^\circ$)	EXACT	-0.967	1.6100	-0.3449	0.0448	-4.785	-6.29
		8.937	0.2189	-0.0784			
	EQUIL/VAR	-0.958	1.6125	-0.3380	0.0449	-4.736	-6.32
		8.863	0.2130	-0.0776			
100	EXACT	-0.576	2.300	-0.3452	-0.1512	-2.972	-7.71
		5.560	0.1871	-0.1819			
	EQUIL/VAR	-0.570	2.2980	-0.3400	-0.1480	-2.937	-7.74
		5.490	0.1850	-0.1790			

CONCLUSIONS

C^0 continuous elements usually show presence of oscillations in the distributions of the stress fields making the judgement of results difficult. Smoothness and interlaminar stress continuity are obtained by the proposed stress recovery procedure, even though the computational resources required are not so demanding. An appropriate evaluation of the interlaminar stress fields leads to an accurate prediction of the onset of delamination. Combined with the finite element software ABAQUS 6.8 the range of applications are significantly broadened. Future developments will concern structures involving subdomains with non-conforming meshes. Attention will be particularly addressed at laminates with dropped plies.

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